

THE THEORY OF THE LANGUAGE FOR COMMUNICATION**Makhmudov Khudoyshukur Alisherovich**Ma'mun University NEI,
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Annotation. This article discusses the language of communication and the theories used in it and their diversity. And detailed information and supplements are given about each theory.

Key words. Modularity, Constituency and Recursion, Theory of Discreteness, The Theory of Productivity, The Theory of Arbitrariness, The Theory of Reliance on Context

Annotation. Ushbu maqolada muloqot tili va shunda qollaniladigan nazariyalar va ularning xilma hilligi haqida gap boradi. Va har bir nazariyalar to'g'risida atroflicha ma'lumotlar va qo'shimchalar beriladi.

Key words. Modularity, Constituency and Recursion, Theory of Discreteness, Theory of Productivity, The theory of Arbitrariness, The Theory of Reliance on Context.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается язык общения и используемые в нем теории и их разнообразие. По каждой теории дана подробная информация и дополнения.

Ключевые слова. Модульность, Избирательность и рекурсия, Теория дискретности, Теория продуктивности, теория произвольности, теория зависимости от контекста.

Over thousands of years of evolution, the human species developed a vocal tract flexible enough to make a wide range of distinguishable sounds and the ability to perceive differences among those sounds. But most important, the human species

developed the ability to use these sounds in systems which could communicate meaning. No one knows just how this happened. Perhaps mental capacities that had evolved for a variety of other adaptive purposes (like fine motor hand–eye coordination) were “re-purposed” to support a complex symbolic and communicative system. Perhaps some mental capacities are exclusively dedicated to language and evolved more gradually along with the increasing complexity of human communication. Or perhaps once they reached a certain level of neurological and cognitive complexity, the synapses of the brain “reorganized” themselves, making the development of language possible. In any case, language is a distinctive attribute of the human species. Although languages differ in many ways, they are all made possible by the same genetic information, they are all processed by the brain in basically the same ways, and, not surprisingly, they all share certain fundamental “design features” and structural characteristics that enable them to work the way they do. For example, although different languages use different sets of sounds, their sounds are organized and combined according to just a few principles. If there were no shared, universal features of language, we would expect the sounds of languages and their combinations to vary randomly. Instead, the sounds of languages and their combinations are limited and systematic. Likewise, all languages follow similar constraints on how they can combine words into phrases and sentences. Understanding and explaining the properties which are universal to all languages – as well as those which vary across languages – is the fundamental job of the linguist.

The theory of Modularity

Most linguists believe that language is a modular system. That is, people produce and interpret language using a set of component subsystems (or modules) in a coordinated way. Each module is responsible for a part of the total job; it takes the output of other modules as its input and distributes its own output to those other modules. Neurolinguistic studies show that different regions of the brain are associated

with different aspects of language processing and, as the following chapters show, dividing language into modules facilitates linguistic analyses greatly.

Some modules have been central to linguistics for a long time. Phonetics is about production and interpretation of speech sounds. Phonology studies the organization of raw phonetics in language in general and in individual languages in particular. Larger linguistic units are the domain of morphology, the study of structure within words – and of syntax, the study of the structure of sentences. Interacting with these modules is the lexicon, the repository of linguistic elements with their meanings and structural properties. In recent decades, philosophers have developed the formal study of semantics (the detailed analysis of literal meaning), and linguistics has incorporated and added to semantics as another module of language. Still more recently, discourse – organization of language above and beyond the sentence – has been recognized by most linguists as another important subsystem of language.

The Theory of Constituency and Recursion

All languages are organized into constituents, allowing more complex units to enter structures where simpler ones are also possible. So we can say in English, “She sat down,” “The smart woman sat down,” “The tall, darkhaired, smart woman with the bright red sweater and pearl necklace sat down.” Being composed of constituents gives language a balance of structure and flexibility. Constituents can be replaced by other constituents, but you can’t replace a constituent with a series of words that is not a constituent. So you can’t replace she with smart with the bright red sweater (“Smart with the bright red sweater sat down” doesn’t work). Constituents can be moved, but you can only move a complete constituent. She is very smart is possible and so is Very smart, she is, but not Smart, she is very.

The Theory of Discreteness

Another property of all languages is discreteness. The range of sounds that human beings can make is continuous, like a slide whistle. For example, you can slide from a high “long e” sound (as in feed) all the way down to a low “short a” sound (as in bat)

and then slide back to a “long o” sound (as in poke) – all in one continuous glide. But all languages divide that continuous space of sound into discrete, incremental territories, just as most western music divides the continuous range of pitch into discrete steps in a scale. Sounds that are discrete in one language may not be discrete in another. In English, for example, we distinguish “short a” from “short e,” so that pat and pet are different words.

Discreteness also shows itself in other modules of language, for example, meaning. The color spectrum is a clear example. Color variation is a continuum – red shades through red-orange to orange to yellow-orange to yellow and so on through the spectrum. But all languages divide the color spectrum into discrete categories, although languages differ in how they divide those continua into words. In some languages there are only two basic color terms, roughly meaning ‘light’ and ‘dark;’ others add red, yellow, and green, whereas still others, including English, have developed words for many more colors¹.

Language is composed of separate sounds, words, sentences and other utterance units. The fact that we hear speech as a sequence of individual sounds, words, and sentences is actually an incredible accomplishment (and all the more incredible for how instantaneously and unconsciously we do it). Acoustically sounds and words blend into each other. (If you have tried to learn a second language as an adult, you know how hard it can be to separate words spoken at a normal conversational pace.) Remarkably, babies only a few weeks old are able to distinguish even closely related sounds in the language of their home from each other and to distinguish the sounds that belong to the language they are learning from the sounds in other languages at a very early age. Furthermore, children in the first year or two of life learn to pick out words from the stream of speech with no instruction.

¹ Fasold R.W. Connor-Linton J. and co-authors. *An Introduction to Language and Linguistics*. –Cambridge. –P.20
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

The theory of Productivity

Another key feature of language is productivity. When people hear a word for the first time, they often ask, “Is that a word?” If they ask a linguist, the answer is likely to be, “It is now.” If the novel word is formed according to the morphological and phonological rules of its language and it is understandable in context, it is a bona fide word, even if it’s not found in a dictionary. Languages can systematically combine the minimal units of meaning, called morphemes, into novel words, whose meaning is nonetheless deducible from the interaction of its morphemic components. Imagine each speaker in the world coining just one new word, and you’ll have some idea of just how productive a language can be. Most of these spontaneous coinings – inspired by a particular context – are not used frequently enough to ever make it into a dictionary, but some coinings do become part of the lexicon because they meet a new need. Productivity is one way in which languages change to meet the changing communicative needs of their speakers.

The theory of Arbitrariness

The productivity of languages derives, in large part, from the fact that they are organized around a finite set of principles which systematically constrain the ways in which sounds, morphemes, words, phrases, and sentences may be combined. A native speaker of a language unconsciously “knows” these principles and can use them to produce and interpret an infinite variety of utterances. Another fundamental property of language is its arbitrariness. With few exceptions, words have no principled or systematic connection with what they mean. In English, the first three numbers are one, two, three – but in Chinese they are yi, er, san. Neither language has the “right” word for the numerals or for anything else, because there is no such thing. Even onomatopoeic words for sounds, like ding-dong and click, that are supposed to sound like the noise they name, actually vary from language to language. The linguist Catherine Ball has created a website listing the sounds various animals make in

different languages around the world². In English, for example, a dog says bow wow or maybe woof woof, but in Hindi it says bho: bho:. Greek dogs say gav and Korean dogs say mung mung. People perceive these sounds through the arbitrary “sound filters” of their respective languages, so even something as seemingly objective as a dog’s bark is in fact represented arbitrarily in language.

The Theory of Reliance on Context

A corollary of arbitrariness – of association between sound sequences and meanings or in the order of words in phrases – is duality. Because there is nothing about the pronunciation of the word one (transcribed phonetically – as it sounds – it would be [wn]) that necessarily associates it with the numeral 1, that same sequence of sounds (but spelled won) can also be used to mean something entirely different, the past tense of the verb win.

Reliance on context is a crucial property of languages, not just in figuring out the meaning of words like one and won, but in interpreting the meaning of entire utterances. The meaning of a sentence depends crucially on the context in which it is uttered. That context could be the sentence or sentences that immediately precede it, or it could be the broader physical or social circumstances in which the sentence is uttered. If someone says “One,” the meaning of that utterance is only clear in the context of a preceding utterance – for example, “Do you want one lump of sugar or two?” Similarly, “It’s cold in here” could be a complaint, a request to close a window, or even a compliment (about a freezer, perhaps). Who or what a given pronoun (like she, it, us, or them) refers to may rely on prior sentences or the immediate physical environment. Languages rely on the connection between form (what is said) and context (when, where, by whom, and to whom it is said) to communicate much more than is contained in a sequence of words.

²<http://www.georgetown.edu/faculty/%20ballc/animals/>

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5. ¹ Bolton, Whitney F. 1982, A living language : the history and structure of English, New York: Random House.-P.5